

Early Detection of Stroke Risk Using Feature-Based Supervised Learning

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Abstract—This project deals with the prediction of the occurrence of stroke in a person using diverse approaches in machine learning. Among many methods, a machine learning model is used and trained on data and is made to predict, focusing on class imbalance and real-world relevance. For a better use case, methods like feature selection and feature engineering were also done by using knowledge in the related domain. Models like CATBoost, Random Forest, and an ensemble approach were used for prediction, and among them, the best was filtered out, looking at the stability and generalization of the model on the unseen data. Compared to all the approaches chosen, the stacking of models provided a stable prediction across the testing data with highly important metrics: Recall. For the transparency and to remove the complex understanding, LIME was used to interpret the process inside the model to decide whether of the stroke case. Overall, this report demonstrates how AI methods and model implementation help in solving complex identification of rare health issues and can be of great help to society.

Keywords— *Stroke Prediction, Imbalanced Data, Stacking Classifier, CATBoost, RF, XGBoost, LIME, Optuna, Recall, F1scores*

I. INTRODUCTION

Stroke occurrence impacts individuals' lives, along with the quality of life for humans. Elimination of such human suffering and tackling it by predicting stroke early will be a great help in the medical field. Confronting the challenge of predicting stroke can save many lives. By applying techniques like machine learning, we aim to identify the patterns for the early detection of stroke (Dritsas & Trigka, 2022). The traditional method for curing strokes has a hurdle, that is, it demands a symptom for it to be diagnosed, whereas predictive models can have a logical and trained estimate of a patient's likelihood of having a stroke before it becomes too late (Chahine et al., 2023).

The dataset used in this research project is from Kaggle — playground series, season 3, episode 2 competition. It contains medical and demographic features of several patients. The dataset, influenced by real healthcare data, is synthetically generated for research and competition. It has approximately 15,000 rows and includes 12 input features such as age, gender, hypertension, and heart disease. The target column is a binary field named "stroke" with values 0 (non-stroke) or 1 (stroke). The dataset used for this study is the training set only, as the test set lacks labels. The domain is healthcare and predictive analysis, where machine learning and medical pattern recognition are applied to improve

medical decision-making. Python was used for development with libraries such as Pandas, NumPy, matplotlib, Seaborn, and Scikit-learn, and the implementation was done in Jupyter Notebook.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Machine Learning in Stroke Prediction

Machine learning (ML) approaches has emerged as one of the promising ways to deal with patterns hidden inside datasets. In medical field, early prediction of diseases can save many lives. Machine learning approaches in medical fields, or in stroke prediction to be precise, are used widely. These methods can predict whether a patient can have a stroke or not based on some features related to the target outcomes. Models used in ML aim to know and uncover complex patterns hidden among clinical and demographic features, such as age, blood pressure, heart disease, and smoking status. Having such hands-on use of these techniques helps in preventing many critical losses of people's lives from stroke deaths (Dritsas & Trigka, 2022).

B. Ensemble and Advanced ML Models

Various model approaches are used for solving hidden patterns in datasets. Whether it be simple or complex, there are combinations of model approaches for every problem. Complex but strong models like CATBoost, XGBoost are very broadly used for the prediction of stroke. Many studies and papers present the work of single models, but a combination of models—i.e, ensemble methods is effective with many clinical and personal features and may yield better outcomes (Yan & Feng, 2022). Beyond just a simple ensemble approach, more advanced methods like stacking have been used to further improve overall outcomes. The base model is first trained independently, and their predictions are used as a feature for the meta-learner. This approach not only improves recall and F1-score but also offers better generalization on unseen imbalanced data (Yassin et al., 2024).

C. Data Imbalance and Feature Selection Problem

Data imbalance is a major problem with stroke prediction as well. Stroke cases are just a small percentage of the dataset—only 4.1%. This makes accuracy misleading and causes the model to miss stroke cases. It is fixed by using techniques like SMOTE-Tomek, which balances oversampling and undersampling to improve balance and

avoid overfitting (Gurcan & Soylu, 2024).

Feature selection and engineering are also very important. Appropriate features include BMI categories, age categories, and health risk factor pairs. Recursive Feature Elimination with Random Forest helps in selecting the most significant features and handles complex relationships without complicating the model (Li et al., 2023). Data augmentation and random sampling also help in improving the training of the model.

D. Challenges and characteristics of Imbalanced Data

Imbalanced datasets present a level of difficulty for healthcare applications, such as stroke prediction. On a classification dataset, one class could be significantly higher or have a high frequency compared to others (Gurcan & Soylu, 2024). In such context traditional machine learning approach would be biased to the majority class, which leads to misleading information. This leads to a poor generalization of the model in the real-world test data where the class imbalance is present. To address this, there are many sampling techniques. Some are under sampling, some are over sampling, and Random sampling. In the further report, A hybrid approach is used as a sampling technique which takes the benefit of the under-sampling and oversampling (More & Rana, 2022).

III. DATA UNDERSTANDING AND PREPARATION

A. Exploratory Data Analysis

The statistical summary of the dataset was obtained to understand the central tendencies and dispersion of the numerical features. The target variable stroke had a mean value of 0.041, indicating that only about 4.1% of the cases in the dataset correspond to individuals who experienced a stroke. After checking the data set there were missing values to deal with in column of bmi. The empty value was filled by replacing with median of the respective column. The distribution seen of the stroke column was plotted using a histogram, seeing that it makes obvious that there is a huge class imbalance i.e only a small portion of the dataset represents stroke case.

Fig 1: Histogram plot

Similarly, histogram of all numerical and categorical features. The aim for this was to get familiar to the spread and distribution of the features and detect potential outliers.

Almost all the feature showed convincing distribution but the avg_glucose_level had some skewness.

Fig 2: Histogram plot of numerical feature

A correlation heatmap was plotted between all the numerical feature to know the influence of individual features in each other and the target column. The heatmap revealed no strong correlation among any predictors. However, a decent correlation could be seen between bmi and age features.

Fig 3: Correlation Heatmap

After the process of visualization, the correlation heatmap provided a good information about the features and its relationship with the target column. Although there were no strong linear correlations between the features or between the feature and the target column, some feature-target patterns were seen. For example, with increase in age, it was seen that the stroke cases appear to increase. To be precise, for the group over 60 age, the stroke had an increase. Likewise, in hypertension and heart disease, it showed a higher frequency of stroke cases compared to those without this condition. And features like gender and residence did not show a strong visual relationship with stroke or occurrence.

As a collective the visualization showed that the default feature volume is not that effective for the prediction of the target. And there is need for the feature engineering and the major thing was the class imbalance, it was causing a lot of discrepancy and this was indeed to be solved.

B. Preprocessing and Feature Engineering

The first step was analyzing the data set: looking for missing value, inconsistent patterns, missing values and irrelevant features. However, the data set had no missing values or even duplicate values. This made it easier to move onto the next step. The feature column: id, was a unique identifier for each record. This information was of no use and could be a potential noise. So, the column was dropped.

To uplift and make the features more meaningful for stronger prediction of stroke classes, several new features were created based on the domain knowledge and feature interactions.

Firstly, the numerical feature bmi and age was categorized in categorical groups. A complete risk factor was created by adding multiple health indicators like age, glucose level, hypertension, smoking status, heart disease, and obesity.

Along with these, many interaction features and medical proxies were made relating to real world medical conditions shown in Fig. 10. New features like age * hypertension,

glucose * BMI were included. Proxies for inflammation, physical inactivity, carotid artery disease and transient ischemic attack were added as features from a domain reference (NHLBI, 2023).

Categorical features having data in the form of binary or ordinal categories were converted into numeric value using label encoding. Numerical features like avg_glucose_level, bmi, obesity and various interaction features were scaled using Standard Scaler. Scaling the numeric features helps make sure features contribute equally during model training and prevents bias (Li et al., 2023).

Considering the high imbalance in data, some data were added from the real dataset version as this current dataset is the synthetic version. The data rows, which were stroke cases, were added to the dataset. This augmentation was done so that the model could get a slight edge on the minority class.

The dataset was split into training and testing sets for training and evaluating model performance using the train_test_split() function in a ratio of 80:20. As the dataset was highly imbalanced, stratified sampling was used to ensure both sets remain consistent.

For selecting impactful features, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) with Random Forest Classifier was used. This approach retains original features and is ideal for imbalanced and medically sensitive data.

In this analysis, SMOTETomek was used for resampling due to severe class imbalance. It combines both oversampling and undersampling (Gurcan & Soylu, 2024). This hybrid method reduces overfitting compared to plain SMOTE or ADYSN and helps maintain a better trade-off between precision and recall for the minority class.

IV. MODELING STRATEGY AND TRAINING

For better and diverse analysis of the stroke dataset, three models (Catboost, Random Forest and Stacking of XGBoost and CatBoost) were implemented. In This section, the selection of each of the models and the direction of their training will be justified with explanation, model training, evaluation and visualization.

The overall goal for the selection of the models was not targeted not only for the accuracy in metrics, considering that the data has heavily imbalanced, the critical importance was given to recall in medical diagnosis with possible balance with precision (Yassin et al., 2024).

A. CatBoost Classifier(Single Model)

As a first model a boosting model: Catboost was selected for the imbalanced problem in the dataset. The goal again was handling class imbalance with high recall and not much loss on F1 score of minority class so this model was chosen.

To ensure that the model does best optuna was used for hyperparameter tuning with a TPE sampler. The optimization targeted F1 Score balance and recall using 5-fold Stratified Cross validation. To get the best parameter that would not

overfit the model, regularization parameter like l2_leaf_reg and shallow depth were used.

The model catboost was initiated using the best hyperparameters found via optuna applying cross validation approach of 5 folds. The training process involved fitting the model on resampled training data and testing was done on the unseen unbalanced testing data.

The evaluation of the model was done in both training and testing sets. The threshold(0.4-0.5) for the class prediction was changed and tested for a good balance of high recall and moderate balance of F1 score.

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	86.84%	84.89%
Recall	0.87	0.8
Precision	0.64	0.61
F1-Score	0.68	0.64

Table 1: Model Evaluation:Macro Avg(Catboost)

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	86.84%	84.89%
Recall(Minority Class)	0.88	0.74
Precision(Minority Class)	0.28	0.23
F1-Score(Minority Class)	0.43	0.36

Table 2: Model Evaluation(Catboost-stroke cases)

Fig 4: Visualization of minority class metrics

Confusion matrices shows a good stroke detection with high recall but low precision.

Fig 5: Confusion matrix

B. Random Forest Classifier(RF)

Random forest combines result of multiple decision trees and Compared to models like SVM, it helps to improve performance and control overfitting in highly imbalance data. Furthermore, it can be extensively tuned to get optimal output.

Random forest was tuned via optuna using cross validation for finding best parameters like n_estimator, max_depths, max_features, and others. After that the model was trained. The model RF used the best hyperparameter from optuna and the resampled data was fitted to the random forest model.

The Evaluation of the model was done on training set and testing set too, the testing set was not oversampled so no risk of data leakage. For testing results the default threshold (0.5) was changed (around 0.4) so that the high recall with possible balance could be achieved.

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	87%	88.10%
Recall	0.87	0.77
Precision	0.64	0.62
F1-Score	0.68	0.66

Table 3: Model Evaluation: Macro Avg (RF)

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	87%	88.10%
Recall(Minority Class)	0.88	0.64
Precision(Minority Class)	0.28	0.27
F1-Score(Minority Class)	0.43	0.38

Table 4: Model Evaluation (RF-Stroke Cases)

Fig 6: Visualization of minority class metrics

Fig 8: Stacking Architecture

The model evaluation was done on both training set and testing set. Threshold tuning was done for better recall while maintaining possible balance in F1 score.

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	89%	89%
Recall	0.80	0.80
Precision	0.64	0.63
F1-Score	0.68	0.67

Table 5: Model Evaluation: Macro Avg (Stacking)

Metrics	Training Performance	Testing Performance
Accuracy	89%	89%
Recall(Minority Class)	0.69	0.70
Precision(Minority Class)	0.30	0.29
F1-Score(Minority Class)	0.42	0.41

Table 6: Model Evaluation (Stacking-Stroke Cases)

Fig 7: Confusion Matrix: Test(RF)

C. STACKING (XGBOOST + CATBOOST, LOGISTIC REGRESSION AS META LEARNER)

For an objective of achieving stability in metrics and for better generalization ensemble method was used combining predictions of base learners to improve generalization. The stacking classifier was in two layers, first the base learners makes prediction and these predictions are used as input features for the meta learners.

The boosting model were a good combination as base learner because it was suitable for imbalanced data and for non- linear relationship. Although the diversity may seem to lack in base learner, the current combination did good compared to diverse stacking of other tree, linear and neural network approaches as base learner.

On other hand logistic regression was an optimal choice as the meta-learner compared to other because it balanced the complexity and didn't let the complexity composition of model to overfit and lower generalization.

Fig 9: Visualization of minority class metrics

Fig 10: Confusion Matrix: Test(RF)

V. BENCHMARKING MODELS FOR FINAL SELECTION

Among the models that were chosen in train, a comparison will be discussed in this section. The result of the metrics is averaged over multiple folds to boost robustness.

A. Precision recall curve

Both model (Catboost and RF) have an average precision of 0.34, threshold of 0.45 and 0.34 was selected respectively for a higher recall. The plot shows drop in precision after moderate recall and shows its limited to balance both

Stacking model performs better with AP of 0.38 at a threshold of 0.49. The model maintains relatively higher precision at different recall points. It is seen that this is a stronger choice for imbalance classification where recall is at priority.

B. Recall, precision, F1 score on testing set across all models

For a better interpretation of the stability of models and to know how well the models were able to generalize, a Bar plot is used for visualization. The best model for this data set is determined by recall and a good balance in F1 score. Compared to Random forest, CatBoost provides a good generalization and a good recall with moderate balance seen by F1 score. However, Stacking seems to be a more stable option with a high recall on such severely imbalanced test data and gives a slightly better balance as per F1 score.

Fig 11: Model Comparison- Balanced average comparison

C. Model Explanation – LIME

For the model transparency Lime was implemented for interpreting Staking model. This approach breaks down complex process with an explanation around the prediction point. Final model in stacking was Calibrated Stacking Classifier, base learners were CATBoost and XGBoost and logistic regression was the meta learner. For feature selection Recursive Feature Elimination was used. As per figure 26, The prediction of class 0 which is no stroke is 80%. For that confident prediction, factors like work_type_private, inflammation_proxy and smoking status had negative contribution to stroke happening case giving class 0 a strong edge.

Even between complex model individual feature affect the model decision. The combination of recursive feature elimination and LIME helped to choose best features and explain the overall approach behind predicting either of the case.

VI. HYPERPARAMETER TUNING

For better training and implementation of the model, hyperparameter tuning and Stratified cross-validation were used. Use of the best hyperparameter led to a good generalization of the model and didn't let the complex model result in overfitting or irrelevant output.

Two tuning methods were used for the model implementation: optuna and Random Search. Grid search was intentionally not used, looking at its computational cost and it's not that efficient in high-dimensional parameters (Alibrahim & Ludwig, 2021). With the default parameters for all models, the problem with poor prediction and even overfitting was clearly seen. By searching best parameter for each model, it helped to regularize the model without making it overly complex. Applying parameter tuning instantly helped to regularize the model and control overfitting, and gave a flexible control over the outcome.

The hyperparameter tuning was done focusing on the recall metrics. By making sure the stroke cases instance was correctly identified, the balance of precision and recall was also not compromised. This approach was important since false negatives carry high cost in medical field.

The imbalanced data surely impacted the result of hyperparameter tuning. Most of the time it leads to a bias to the majority class. Tuning is handled very carefully to Counter this issue. For the models, class weight and stratified sampling was used during cross validation.

VII. CONCLUSION

For the overall summarization, despite the significant class imbalance, use of careful tuning and prioritizing a well appreciated metrics helped on solving and predicting stroke cases. Among all the models, the stacking of boosting algorithm helps to generalize well on the unseen test data.

Handling synthetic and highly imbalanced datasets came with a lot of challenges, including a high risk of overfitting and noise. Use of sampling techniques like SMOTE Tomek helped a lot in training the model. Feature elimination and a concise explanation of the model approach by LIME helped a lot to understand the problem and solve it deeply.

While LIME helped, the limitation of the dataset is still there. During the training and evaluation of the model, it was clear that the prediction was so limited by its synthetic and imbalanced nature for the minority class. Keeping all these in mind, using deep learning models, such as neural networks, could identify the complex pattern between the data, and using such is part of the future work.

VIII. REFERENCE

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